

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Theoretical structural study of van der Waals complexes between oxazole and atmospheric gases CO₂ and N₂ for capture applications.

[version 1; peer review: awaiting peer review]

A. Belasri¹, F. Tahiri¹, O. Douass¹, S. Dalbouha¹

¹Laboratory of Organic and Physical Chemistry, Research Team: Molecular Modeling, Materials, and Environment, Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Sciences Agadir, Ibn Zohr University, Agadir, Morocco, B.P. 8106, Morocco

²Optics, Material and Systems Team, , Faculty of Sciences, Abdelmalek Essâadi University, B.P. 2121, M'Hannech II, 93030 Tétouan, Morocco

³Facultad de Ingeniería, Núcleo de Astroquímica & Astrofísica, Universidad Autónoma de Chile, Av. Pedro de Valdivia 425, Providencia, Santiago, Chile

⁴Physical and Theoretical Chemistry, University of Wuppertal, Wuppertal, Germany

⁵Department of Chemistry, College of Sciences, King Saud University, P.O. Box 2455, Riyadh, 11451, Saudi Arabia

⁶Departamento de Química y Física, Instituto de Estructura de la Materia, Madrid, Unidad Asociada GIFMAN, CSIC-UHU, Spain

V1 First published: 08 Jan 2025, 5:3
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.18925.1>

Latest published: 08 Jan 2025, 5:3
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.18925.1>

Open Peer Review

Approval Status AWAITING PEER REVIEW

Any reports and responses or comments on the article can be found at the end of the article.

Abstract

Background

The objective of this study is to explore the potential of oxazole (C₃H₃NO), a fascinating heterocyclic compound naturally present, which is a potential ligand in the construction of Metal Organic Frameworks (MOF's) for the selective capture of CO₂ in a nitrogen-rich atmosphere, by using both molecular and solid-state simulation techniques.

Methods

This study investigates the equilibrium structures and binding energies of van der Waals aggregates formed by an oxazole molecule with nonpolar molecules such as CO₂ and N₂, considering both two-body systems (oxazole@CO₂ and oxazole@N₂) and three-body systems (oxazole@CO₂@N₂ and oxazole-CO₂/N₂@Au₆/Cu₆/Zn₃₀3). Molecular computations for these systems are conducted using ab initio calculations at the MP2/aug-cc-pVXZ level of theory, where X = (D, T). Additionally, solid-state simulations analyze the adsorption

behaviors and energies of oxazole@CO₂ and oxazole@N₂ on metallic surfaces: Au, Cu, ZnO(111) through Monte Carlo methods.

Results

We find that the oxazole exhibits more adsorption selectivity for CO₂ than for N₂. Adding a second gas to the most stable complexes, oxazole@CO₂ and oxazole@N₂, the oxazole capture ability does not vary. On the contrary, it strengthens the adsorption energy of three-body complexes compared to two-body complexes. The addition of metallic clusters (Au₆, Cu₆, Zn₃O₃) and metallic surfaces (Au, Cu, ZnO) enhances the adsorption capacity, where Cu₆ is particularly highly efficient. Both ZnO and Cu surfaces offer significant adsorption advantages while remaining economically feasible.

Conclusions

This study demonstrates that oxazole exhibits a strong selectivity for CO₂ over N₂, with the addition of metallic clusters and surfaces significantly enhancing its adsorption capacity. These findings highlight the potential of oxazole-based materials for effective gas capture and separation, with positive implications for environmental sustainability.

Plain language summary

This research project focuses on gas capture and separation, especially for molecules like carbon dioxide (CO₂) and nitrogen (N₂), which are crucial in both industrial and environmental contexts. Metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) show promise for efficient CO₂ capture due to their adjustable structures and large surface areas. However, the use of oxazole, a specific molecule, for CO₂ capture in these structures has been little explored. This study examines how oxazole interacts with CO₂ and N₂ molecules, forming aggregates bound by van der Waals forces (a type of molecular attraction). Results show that oxazole favors binding with CO₂ over nitrogen, making it potentially useful for gas separation. By adding metallic clusters, such as gold, copper, or zinc oxide, the adsorption capacity of oxazole further improves, especially with copper, while remaining affordable.

This study highlights oxazole's potential for effective gas capture, contributing to more sustainable and environmentally friendly technologies.

Keywords

Adsorption, CO₂ capture, N₂, atmosphere, ab initio, MOF's.

This article is included in the [Marie-Sklodowska-Curie Actions \(MSCA\) gateway](#).

This article is included in the [Horizon 2020 gateway](#).

This article is included in the [Computational Chemistry collection](#).

Corresponding author: S. Dalbouha (s.dalbouha@uiz.ac.ma)

Author roles: **Belasri A:** Data Curation, Investigation; **Tahiri F:** Investigation, Visualization; **Douass O:** Data Curation, Visualization; **Inostroza-Pino N:** Formal Analysis, Software; **Belmouden M:** Formal Analysis, Methodology; **Bahmann H:** Supervision; **Mogren Al-Mogren M:** Formal Analysis, Visualization; **Senent ML:** Methodology, Project Administration, Validation, Writing – Original Draft Preparation; **Dalbouha S:** Conceptualization, Data Curation, Investigation, Supervision, Writing – Original Draft Preparation

Competing interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Grant information: This project has received funding from the [European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme][European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme] under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No [872081] (ATMOS).

The funders had no role in study design, data collection and analysis, decision to publish, or preparation of the manuscript.

Copyright: © 2025 Belasri A *et al.* This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

How to cite this article: Belasri A, Tahiri F, Douass O *et al.* **Theoretical structural study of van der Waals complexes between oxazole and atmospheric gases CO₂ and N₂ for capture applications. [version 1; peer review: awaiting peer review]** Open Research Europe 2025, 5:3 <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.18925.1>

First published: 08 Jan 2025, 5:3 <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.18925.1>

Introduction

The exploration of carbon dioxide capture and separation from gas mixtures by adsorption based on porous materials searching for low-costs and high efficiency, has been a focal point in research¹⁻⁷, aiming to address environmental concerns and enhance industrial processes^{5,6}. Gas adsorption and separation, particularly involving quadrupolar species such as carbon dioxide (CO₂) and nitrogen (N₂), have gained considerable interest due to their importance in industrial and environmental contexts. Metal-organic frameworks (MOF's) are porous crystalline materials formed by organic structures that act as ligands⁸ connected by metal ions or clusters^{9,10}. They have been considered to be efficient for CO₂ capture tools owing to their adjustable and tunable structures², extensive surfaces^{11,12}, large surface areas^{13,14}, customizable functionalities^{15,16}, and high mechanical and thermal stabilities¹⁷. Specific organic ligands, such as heterocycles like carboxylic acids^{18,19}, amines²⁰, imidazoles²¹⁻²⁵, triazoles²⁶, pyridines²⁷, benzenes²⁸, naphthalenes²⁹, benzimidazoles³⁰, etc., enables the regulation of MOF's properties, thereby enhancing their capability for selective adsorption and thermal stability³¹, making them particularly suitable for gas adsorption and separation processes³². MOF's based on imidazole have gained interest due to the ability to design various types of architectures such as rigid, flexible, interpenetrating, etc., to influence the size of cavity pores and different types of supramolecular interactions within the pore^{33,34}.

In our previous study²¹⁻²⁴, we highlighted the significant ability of imidazole to form van der Waals complexes with several greenhouse gases, including CO₂, CH₄, and SF₆, as well as with pollutants such as SO₂ and NH₃ and gas such as CO. This interaction is particularly relevant for selectively capturing CO₂ from mixtures containing these gases. Although oxazole (C₃H₃NO) is a fascinating heterocyclic compound naturally present³⁵, its capacity as a ligand in the construction of CO₂ capturing MOF's has not been thoroughly investigated. This provides an opportunity for further research aimed to valorize the properties of oxazole in developing efficient MOF's for CO₂ capture, contributing to advancements in environmental sustainability and gas separation technologies. Our goal is the theoretical characterization of van der Waals aggregates formed with one oxazole molecule and nonpolar molecules such as carbon dioxide (CO₂) and nitrogen (N₂). CO₂ is known to have significant environmental impacts on global weather patterns and human life³⁶. Anthropogenic emissions of N₂ can indirectly lead to an increase in NO_x levels in the atmosphere. When N₂ reacts with atmospheric oxygen, it converts into nitrogen oxides (NO_x) such as NO and NO₂. These NO_x compounds have consequences on air quality, human health, and the environment, contributing to smog formation, acid rain, and causing harmful effects on respiratory systems and lung tissues³⁷.

In this work, we perform a systematic evaluation of ligands containing both nitrogen and oxygen for their interaction energies with CO₂ and N₂ by using both molecular and

solid-state simulation techniques. In the first approach we use the possible accurate ab initio methods to calculate the binding energies (BEs) of the two-body systems (CO₂-Oxazole-BEs & N₂-Oxazole-BEs). The analysis of the ternary systems (CO₂-oxazole-N₂-BEs) and (oxazole-CO₂/N₂@Au₆/Cu₆/Zn₃O₃) using the same method was conducted to understand the interactions among CO₂, oxazole, and N₂ within these systems, to examine their influence on CO₂ separation and capture strategies in gas mixtures and predict the capacity of new materials to selectively capture and store CO₂ over N₂ in N₂-rich atmospheres. Indeed, the presence of N₂ can significantly influence CO₂ capture performance in MOF's, taking into account their common presence in atmospheric and industrial environments, emphasizing the crucial role of computational methods in designing nanomaterials for carbon capture technologies.

On the other hand, the Monte Carlo solid-state simulations were employed to investigate the interactions between oxazole and the (111) surfaces of Au, Cu, and ZnO. These materials were selected for their unique electronic properties and practical relevance. Gold (Au) is frequently used as a reference due to its stability and well-characterized surface chemistry³⁸. Copper (Cu) is chosen for their economic viability and their proven effectiveness in enhancing adsorption processes³⁹. While the zinc oxide ZnO, was included in this study for their unique semiconducting, piezoelectric, and photoelectric properties and high surface area⁴⁰.

Computational details

All the electronic computations were performed using both the Gaussian 09 Revision C.01 software⁴¹ and the Material Studio (BIOVIA, 2020) program⁴². An appropriate free alternative software for this purpose are GAMESS (US), a powerful tool for electronic structure calculations that supports HF, DFT, MP2, and other methods, and ORCA, a versatile quantum chemistry program renowned for its computational efficiency and support for DFT, HF, and post-HF techniques.

We have combined the most accurate possible ab initio method, and Monte Carlo solid-state simulations⁴³, to investigate the interaction between CO₂ and N₂ and oxazole (Oxa), either isolated, attached to a gold, copper and ZnO cluster or surface.

The study employed the second-order Møller–Plesset theory (MP2)^{44,45} within the Gaussian software to compute the equilibrium structures and spectroscopic properties of both isolated species and complexes included two-body systems like oxazole@CO₂ and oxazole@N₂. Additionally, the three-body systems such as oxazole@CO₂@N₂ and oxazole-CO₂/N₂@Au₆/Cu₆/Zn₃O₃ were investigated. For accurate depiction of small systems. In these computations, the atoms were described using Dunning and co-workers' aug-cc-pVXZ basis set (abbreviated as AVXZ, where X=D, T)⁴⁶, augmented with diffuse atomic orbitals to capture long-range interactions. Specifically, AVTZ was employed for oxazole@CO₂ and oxazole@N₂, while AVDZ was used for oxazole@CO₂@N₂ and oxazole@CO₂/N₂@ cluster complexes.

Monte Carlo is a powerful computational technique used to model the adsorption of molecules on surfaces and to determine the adsorption energy associated with them. In this work, the adsorption energies of oxazole, oxazole@N₂, and oxazole@CO₂ on a gold, copper, or zinc oxide surface were researched by employing the software Materials Studio (BIOVIA, 2020)⁴². As a free alternative to Material Studio, I recommend the open-source software Quantum ESPRESSO and CP2K. The first program, Quantum ESPRESSO, is a comprehensive suite for quantum simulations, ideal for materials modeling and the simulation of solids, liquids, and nanostructures.

<https://www.quantum-espresso.org/>

The second program, CP2K, is also free and open-source software, widely used for molecular dynamics simulations and quantum chemistry calculations, particularly for systems with large numbers of atoms.

<https://www.cp2k.org/>

The Au, Cu, and ZnO crystal structures have been imported from the Materials Studio database. Surfaces were built by clicking 'Build', then 'Surface', and then 'Cleave Surface'. In the following menu, the cleaving plane (1 1 1) has been chosen, and then afterward, the 'Symmetry' option was used to construct a supercell. All the surface structures were prepared with three layers, as illustrated in Figure 5.

The structures of oxazole, oxazole@N₂, and oxazole@CO₂ were well optimized following the then possible lowest energy using the COMPASS II force field as implemented in the Forcite Module. This same force field was used in the Monte Carlo simulations. The simulations were done utilizing the Adsorption Locator Module in the materials studio 2020 package from BIOVIA. The COMPASS II force field is useful in handling adsorption processes; therefore, it works best in catalysis, materials science, and environmental science.

Therefore, a detailed investigation of adsorption behaviors and energies of the fixed molecules on the chosen surfaces gave valuable insight into their eventual interactions and stability.

The minimum character of all the optimized structures is evidenced by the presence of all positive harmonic frequencies, indicates that the system is at its energy minimum, reflecting a stable and optimized configuration. The binding energy (BE) between the oxazole and CO₂ or N₂ was evaluated for optimized geometries using Second order Möller-Plesset theory (MP2) in connection with aug-cc-pVTZ basis set (denoted in this paper by AVTZ). The binding energies (BEs) were calculated using the following energy expression:

$$BE = E_{\text{Complex}} - (E_{\text{oxazole}} + E_{\text{gaz}})$$

where: *BE* is the binding energy, E_{complex} is the total energy of the oxazole-gas complex, E_{Oxazole} is the total energy of the isolated oxazole molecule, and E_{gaz} is the total energy of the

isolated gas molecule (CO₂ or N₂). For a more accurate estimation of the interaction energy, the basis set superposition error (BSSE) was corrected using the Boys and Bernardi method⁴⁷. Additionally, the zero-point vibrational energy correction (ZPVE) was also taken into account for all geometries⁴⁸.

For the complexes between the oxazole and CO₂ or N₂ @ cluster (Au₆, Cu₆ or Zn₃O₃) we employed the MP2/AVDZ/LanL2DZ⁴⁹, and for the adsorption of CO₂ and N₂ on Au, Cu, and ZnO (111) surfaces we used the Monte Carlo computational technique.

The binding energies (BEs) were calculated using the following energy expression:

$$BE = E_{\text{Complex}} - (E_{\text{Oxa@CO2/N2}} + E_{\text{Cluster/Surface}})$$

where: *BE* is the binding energy E_{complex} is the total energy of the Oxa CO₂/N₂@ cluster (cluster = Au₆/Cu₆ or Zn₃O₃) or Surface Au, Cu or ZnO (111) complexes, $E_{\text{Oxa@CO2/N2}}$ is the total energy of the complex Oxazole+CO₂ or Oxazole+N₂, and $E_{\text{Cluster/Surface}}$ is the total energy of the isolated gas cluster (Au₆, Cu₆ or Zn₃O₃) or Surface Au(111), Cu (111) or ZnO (111). For a more accurate estimation of the interaction energy of Oxazole CO₂/N₂@ cluster (cluster= Au₆/Cu₆ or Zn₃O₃) the zero-point vibrational energy correction (ZPVE) was also taken into account for all geometries.

Results and discussions

Equilibrium structure of the complexes

To examine the molecular-level adsorption of CO₂ and N₂ on oxazole, we first located the CO₂ and N₂ molecules at the N1 site of oxazole (refer to Figure 1), and then we oriented them around it to explore all possible equilibrium structures. It's worth noting that the number of stable structures increases the likelihood of gas capture. Despite multiple attempts, the optimization results at the MP2/AVTZ level consistently converge towards one of the structures presented in Figure 1A and B, which characterize the complexes formed by oxazole with CO₂ and N₂.

The study carried out at the MP2/AVTZ level on the CO₂-Oxazole complex reveals the existence of two stable structures labeled I1 and I2 (cf. Figure 2A, Table 1). In structure I1 ($E_r = 0.0$ kcal/mol), identified as the global minimum, the bond is established through an interaction between the electron donor-acceptor (EDA) sites of CO₂ and oxazole (RO10-H6 = 2.6956 Å and RC9-N1 = 2.8418 Å). However, in structure I2 ($E_r = 1.31$ kcal/mol), the bond is maintained through a donor-acceptor electron exchange (EDA), where the oxygen atom of CO₂ interacts with H8 of oxazole (RO10H8 = 2.7362 Å) and the carbon atom of CO₂ interacts with the oxygen of oxazole (RC9-O4 = 2.8340 Å).

Additionally, the study of the complex between N₂ and oxazole, still at the MP2/AVTZ level, revealed the existence of four adsorption sites as outlined in Figure 2B and Table 3.

Figure 1. The atom labelling of the complex Oxazole + CO₂ (A), Oxazole + N₂ (B) and Oxazole and the five principal complexation pathways, I1, I2, I3, I4 and I5 (C).

Figure 2. The equilibrium geometries and the MP2/AVTZ relative energies of the oxazole + CO₂ (A) and oxazole + N₂ (B) Van-der-Waals complexes.

These sites are labeled as follows: I1A ($E_r = 0.0$ kcal/mol), I1B ($E_r = 0.01$ kcal/mol), I2A ($E_r = 0.28$ kcal/mol), and I5 ($E_r = 0.57$ kcal/mol). These distinct structures depict various stable configurations of the N₂-oxazole complex. Predominantly, the key interactions observed in the stable structures occur

where hydrogen bonds link N₂ to oxazole. Additionally, the equilibrium distances within the van der Waals system RN9H_x (X=6,7,8) exhibit the following variations: RN9H6 = 2.7302 Å for I1A, RN9H7 = 2.7437 Å for I1B, RN9H6 = 2.7529 Å for I2A, and RN9H8 = 2.5885 Å for I5.

Table 1. Total electronic energies (E , in a.u.), relative energies (E_r , in cm^{-1}) and structural parameters (Distances in Å; angles in degrees) of the two equilibrium structures of the Oxazole- CO_2 complexes calculated with MP2/aug-cc-pVTZ.

Oxazole (C1)		I1 (C1)		I2 (C1)	
		ROH RCN	2.6956 2.8418	ROH RCO	2.7362 2.8340
E	-245.639836	E	-433.968056	E	-433.965972
		E_r	0.0	E_r	457.2
C2N1	1.2996	C2N1	1.3011	C2N1	1.2987
C3N1	1.3862	C3N1	1.3858	C3N1	1.3869
O4C2	1.3552	O4C2	1.3531	O4C2	1.3570
C5C3	1.3596	C5C3	1.3597	C5C3	1.3593
H6C2	1.0755	H6C2	1.0757	H6C2	1.0757
H7C3	1.0752	H7C3	1.0752	H7C3	1.0752
H8C5	1.0739	H8N4	1.0739	H8N4	1.0741
C3N1C2	104.0	C3N1C2	104.2	C3N1C2	104.1
O4C2N1	114.7	O4C2N1	114.5	O4C2N1	114.6
C5C3N1	109.1	C5C3N1	109.0	C5C3N1	109.3
H6C2N1	128.6	H6C2N1	128.2	H6C2N1	128.8
H7C3N1	122.1	H7C3N1	122.1	H7C3N1	122.0
H8C5O4	116.7	H8C5O4	116.8	H8C5O4	116.6
CO ₂					
E	-188.321641				
CO	1.1702	O10C9	1.1718	O10C9	1.1709
		O11C9	1.1686	O11C9	1.1690
<OCO	180.0	<OCO	177.6	<OCO	179.3
		O10H6	2.6956	O10H8	2.7362
		O10H6C2	104.2	O10H8C5	111.2
		C9O10H6	114.7	C9O10H8	113.6
		C9N1	2.8418	C9O4	2.8340
		C9N1C2	106.8	C9O4C2	142.8
		O10C9N1	86.1	O10C9O4	85.8

Table 1 and Table 3 present the structural parameters at the MP2/AVTZ level, while Table 2 and Table 4 provide the MP2/AVTZ harmonic frequencies for each examined complex. The parameters of the van der Waals aggregates are compared to those of the corresponding isolated components.

During the formation of weak intramolecular bonds, the structure of the oxazole ring and N₂ undergoes minimal changes (see

Table 1 and Table 3). However, a significant deformation is observed in the CO₂ molecule, resulting in the loss of its symmetry. This deformation is particularly pronounced in the oxazole-CO₂ complexes I1 and I2 (see Table 1), where the C-O bond in CO₂ tends to shorten (O11C9: 1.1686 Å for I1, 1.1690 Å for I2) while the distance O10C9 is elongated (1.1718 Å for I1, 1.1709 Å for I2), compared to free CO₂ (CO=1.1702 Å). Additionally, the <OCO angle is bent away

Table 2. Harmonic fundamental frequencies (ω , in cm^{-1}) of CO_2 , oxazole, and the two equilibrium geometries of the oxazole- CO_2 complexes calculated at the MP2/AVTZ level of theory.

	ω			
	Oxazole	CO_2	I1	I2
ω_1	a 3330		a 3331	a 3330
ω_2	3311		3312	3309
ω_3	3299		3300	3299
ω_4		σ_u 2402	2402	2404
ω_5	1546		1546	1547
ω_6	1508		1506	1507
ω_7	1355		1355	1354
ω_8		σ_g 1326	1327	1328
ω_9	1272		1269	1270
ω_{10}	1185		1189	1182
ω_{11}	1141		1144	1138
ω_{12}	1109		1111	1108
ω_{13}	1086		1086	1082
ω_{14}	915		917	917
ω_{15}	905		909	904
ω_{16}	864		865	868
ω_{17}	827		836	827
ω_{18}	763		766	771
ω_{19}	665		667	664
ω_{20}		π 659	662	660
ω_{21}		π 659	637	651
ω_{22}	628		628	626
ω_{23}			132	100
ω_{24}			88	80
ω_{25}			52	39
ω_{26}			44	38
ω_{27}			29	21

from the linear configuration of a free CO_2 molecule, measuring 177.6 degrees for I1 and 179.3 degrees for I2, respectively. This deformation is attributed to the formation of the van der Waals complexes between CO_2 and oxazole, leading to electron redistribution and strengthening of the C-O bond.

Harmonic frequencies were computed to ensure minimal energy for all structures. Notably, in Table 2 and Table 4,

certain low frequencies (5 frequencies for Oxazole- CO_2 , ω_{23} - ω_{27} , and for Oxazole- N_2 , ω_{20} - ω_{24}) emerge, which were not observed for the monomers. This situation allows for the use of a Born-Oppenheimer-type approach, which distinguishes between intramolecular and intermolecular vibrations. Intermolecular vibrations more closely resemble hindered rotations or tunneling motions. Generally, there is a strong coupling between different intermolecular degrees of freedom. The deformation vibrations of O-C-O in complexes I1 and I2 occur at frequencies of 637 cm^{-1} and 651 cm^{-1} , respectively. These modes experience significant frequency shifts compared to the CO_2 monomer, approximately 8 cm^{-1} for complex I2 and 22 cm^{-1} for complex I1. Furthermore, the symmetric and antisymmetric intermolecular O-C stretching modes with frequencies $\omega_8 = 1328 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\omega_4 = 2402 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for complex I2 have shifted by 2 cm^{-1} from frequencies of $\omega_8 = 1326 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\omega_4 = 2404 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for the CO_2 monomer. In the oxazole- N_2 complex, the stretching of N-N is not influenced by the formation of the hydrogen bond between the N of N_2 and the H of oxazole. Thus, the intermolecular stretching vibrations H...N-N(ω_{21}) in the optimal structure are observed at frequencies of 63 cm^{-1} , 58 cm^{-1} , 54 cm^{-1} , and 57 cm^{-1} for I1A, I1B, I2A, and I5, respectively.

Binding energies

Two body complexes type oxazole- CO_2 and oxazole- N_2

The binding energy is crucial for understanding, predicting, and enhancing the performance of adsorbent materials in greenhouse gas and pollutant capture processes. It determines the interaction between the host and the guest, as well as the properties of the adsorbent material. A more negative adsorption energy generally indicates a stronger adsorption interaction. For this reason, the binding energies of all previously mentioned stable forms, are computed via the MP2/AVTZ approach and including the zero-point vibrational energy (ZPE) along with as well as the Boys and Bernardi correction (BSSE), are listed in Table 5. Our calculations indicate that oxazole is favored energetically as an adsorbent for both our adsorbates although CO_2 shows a higher capacity to bind oxazole rings. The range of CO_2 binding energies spans from -4.13 to -2.82 kcal/mol, while for N_2 , the energies range from -1.77 to -1.19 kcal/mol. Based on the adsorption energies, the nitrogen site of the oxazole is the most stable site for CO_2 adsorption, and Hydrogen 6 is the most stable site for N_2 adsorption. The zero-point vibrational energy (ZPE) correction ranges from 0.39 to 0.51 kcal/mol for the CO_2 complexes and from 0.32 to 0.39 kcal/mol for the N_2 complexes. On the other hand, the BSSE correction is between 0.02 and 0.09 kcal/mol for CO_2 and 0.05 kcal/mol for N_2 .

Three body complexes type CO_2 -Oxazole- N_2

Since this article focuses on the CO_2 separation properties relative to N_2 , the most abundant gas in Earth's atmosphere (78.084%)⁵⁰, our aim is to understand, at the molecular level, whether oxazole-based MOF's can simultaneously capture two different gases and how the CO_2 capture capacity varies in the presence of N_2 , which a third body can alter the interaction between two bodies. To achieve this, we performed geometry optimizations on three-body systems, namely N_2 -oxazole- CO_2 ,

Table 3. Total electronic energies (*E*, in a.u.), relative energies (*E_r*, in cm⁻¹) and structural parameters (Distances in Å; angles in degrees) of the four equilibrium structures of the Oxazole-N₂ complex calculated with MP2/aug-cc-pVTZ.

Oxazole (C1)		I1A (C1)		I1B (C1)		I2A (C1)		I5 (C1)	
		<i>R_{NH}</i>	2.7302	<i>R_{NH}</i>	2.7437	<i>R_{NH}</i>	2.7529	<i>R_{NH}</i>	2.5885
<i>E</i>	-245.639836	<i>E</i>	-355.007379	<i>E</i>	-355.007363	<i>E</i>	-355.006923	<i>E</i>	-355.006474
		<i>E_r</i>	0.0	<i>E_r</i>	4	<i>E_r</i>	101	<i>E_r</i>	203
<i>C2N1</i>	2.9962	<i>C2N1</i>	1.3003	<i>C2N1</i>	1.30006	<i>C2N1</i>	1.2997	<i>C2N1</i>	1.2998
<i>C3N1</i>	1.38622	<i>C3N1</i>	1.3860	<i>C3N1</i>	1.3867	<i>C3N1</i>	1.3859	<i>C3N1</i>	1.3863
<i>O4C2</i>	1.35519	<i>O4C2</i>	1.3549	<i>O4C2</i>	1.3547	<i>O4C2</i>	1.3565	<i>O4C2</i>	1.3550
<i>C5C3</i>	1.35957	<i>C5C3</i>	1.3597	<i>C5C3</i>	1.3597	<i>C5C3</i>	1.3597	<i>C5C3</i>	1.3599
<i>H6C2</i>	1.07554	<i>H6C2</i>	1.0754	<i>H6C2</i>	1.0756	<i>H6C2</i>	1.0752	<i>H6C2</i>	1.0755
<i>H7C3</i>	1.07521	<i>H7C3</i>	1.0752	<i>H7C3</i>	1.0751	<i>H7C3</i>	1.0752	<i>H7C3</i>	1.0752
<i>H8C5</i>	1.07390	<i>H8C5</i>	1.0739	<i>H8C5</i>	1.07388	<i>H8C5</i>	1.0733	<i>H8C5</i>	1.0738
<i>C3N1C2</i>	103.99	<i>C3N1C2</i>	104.0	<i>C3N1C2</i>	104.0	<i>C3N1C2</i>	104.0	<i>C3N1C2</i>	104.0
<i>O4C2N1</i>	114.70	<i>O4C2N1</i>	114.7	<i>O4C2N1</i>	114.7	<i>O4C2N1</i>	114.6	<i>O4C2N1</i>	114.7
<i>C5C3N1</i>	109.13	<i>C5C3N1</i>	109.1	<i>C5C3N1</i>	109.1	<i>C5C3N1</i>	109.1	<i>C5C3N1</i>	109.2
<i>H6C2N1</i>	128.59	<i>H6C2N1</i>	128.4	<i>H6C2N1</i>	128.6	<i>H6C2N1</i>	128.8	<i>H6C2N1</i>	128.7
<i>H7C3N1</i>	122.09	<i>H7C3N1</i>	122.1	<i>H7C3N1</i>	122.0	<i>H7C3N1</i>	122.1	<i>H7C3N1</i>	122.0
<i>H8C5O4</i>	116.75	<i>H8C5O4</i>	116.9	<i>H8C5O4</i>	116.8	<i>H8C5O4</i>	116.8	<i>H8C5O4</i>	116.7
	<i>N₂</i>								
<i>E</i>	-109.364800								
<i>NN</i>	1.11401	<i>NN</i>	1.11387		1.11408		1.11396		1.11401
		<i>N9H6</i>	2.7302	<i>N9H7</i>	2.7437	<i>N9H6</i>	2.7529	<i>N9H8</i>	2.5885
		<i>N9H6C2</i>	109.2	<i>N9H7C3</i>	113.3	<i>N9H6C2</i>	114.9	<i>N9H8C5</i>	167.7
		<i>N10N9H6</i>	147.3	<i>N10N9H7</i>	144.1	<i>N10N9H6</i>	114.9	<i>N10N9H8</i>	172.1

starting from various configurations where CO₂ and N₂ occupy the equilibrium positions of the two-body systems, oxazole-CO₂ and oxazole-N₂. Then, we examined the capture of the second gas. The resulting structures are presented in Table 6 and illustrated in Figure 3, in Figure 3A, the equilibrium structures of three systems are shown, obtained using the equilibrium configurations of the oxazole-CO₂ complex and rotating N₂ around oxazole. However, in Figure 3B, the equilibrium structures of three other systems are displayed, obtained using the equilibrium configurations of the oxazole-N₂ complex and rotating CO₂ around oxazole. The structures in Figure 3A are identified by the symbol “InIm,” where “In” and “Im” respectively represent the main complexation pathways (I1, I2, I3, I4, and I5) of CO₂ and N₂ with oxazole (Figure 1C), while in Figure 3B, they are identified by the symbol “ImIn”. The binding energies in Table 6 are determined by combining the AVDZ basis set with MP2 correlation, which is an appropriate method for three-body systems. We opted for AVDZ

over AVTZ due to the size of the systems, which makes the use of AVTZ impossible. These values are then compared to those of two-body complexes (oxazole+X, where X= CO₂, N₂) calculated using the same level of theory. It is observed that the presence of a second gas appears to be beneficial, thereby enhancing the oxazole’s ability to capture both CO₂ and N₂ without causing competition.

The interaction energies of the three-body systems increase, is higher than in the case of the two-body oxazole + CO₂ complexes. In the case of the oxazole-N₂+CO₂ complexes, the binding energy ranges between -3.60 kcal/mol and -5.03 kcal/mol, compared to the two-body systems, oxazole+N₂, whose binding energies are respectively between -1.40 kcal/mol and -1.94 kcal/mol. So, for the oxazole-CO₂+N₂ complexes, the binding energy ranges between -5.94 kcal/mol and -8.40 kcal/mol, compared to the two-body systems oxazole+CO₂, which exhibit binding energies ranging from -3.13 kcal/mol to -4.48 kcal/mol.

Table 4. Harmonic fundamental frequencies (ω , in cm^{-1}) of N_2 , oxazole and the four equilibrium geometries of the oxazole- N_2 complexes calculated at the MP2/AVTZ level.

		Ω											
		Oxazole		N_2		I1A		I1B		I2A		I5	
ω_1	a	3330				a	3330	a	3330	a	3329	a	3336
ω_2		3310					3314		3310		3316		3310
ω_3		3298					3298		3301		3298		3299
ω_4			σ_g	2187			2186		2185		2186		2186
ω_5		1545					1544		1545		1545		1546
ω_6		1507					1506		1507		1506		1508
ω_7		1355					1354		1354		1355		1356
ω_8		1271					1271		1271		1271		1273
ω_9		1185					1186		1186		1182		1186
ω_{10}		1141					1142		1140		1141		1141
ω_{11}		1109					1109		1110		1108		1113
ω_{12}		1085					1086		1086		1085		1085
ω_{13}		915					914		915		914		915
ω_{14}		904					905		904		904		905
ω_{15}		863					864		870		865		866
ω_{16}		826					834		827		833		827
ω_{17}		763					765		764		763		784
ω_{18}		664					666		665		665		665
ω_{19}		627					628		628		627		630
ω_{20}							84		82		77		58
ω_{21}							63		58		54		57
ω_{22}							46		46		42		49
ω_{23}							40		43		26		22
ω_{24}							21		20		13		9

Table 5. MP2/AVTZ binding energies of the oxazole complexes (E_b , kcal/mol).

Complex	E_{int}	$E_{int} + BSSE$	$E_{int} + ZPVE$	$E_{int} + BSSE + ZPE$
Oxazole- CO_2				
I1	-4.13	-4.22	-3.62	-3.71
I2	-2.82	-2.84	-2.43	-2.45
Oxazole- ON_2				
I1A	-1.77	-1.72	-1.38	-1.33
I1B	-1.76	-1.71	-1.39	-1.37
I2A	-1.48	-1.43	-1.16	-1.11
I5	-1.19	-1.14	-0.85	-0.8

This is explained by the formation of an additional intramolecular bond between the molecules of the three systems (π -stacking and Van der Waals interactions), which can stabilize the systems. The inclusion of the ZPE vibrational correction results in a decrease in the energy quantities of three systems, ranging from -0.49 kcal/mol to -1.09 kcal/mol.

Oxa@Au₆, Cu₆ and Zn₃O₃, and CO₂/N₂-Ox@Au₆, Cu₆ and Zn₃O₃
 Recently, various technologies have emerged for CO₂ capture, utilizing methods such as chemisorption and physisorption, due to the development of nanodevices such as metal nanoclusters and metal oxide nanoclusters⁵¹. Metal and metal oxide nanocomposite materials have been particularly used in a wide range of applications, including energy storage⁵², drug delivery⁵³, and the adsorptive removal of a diverse range of pollutants from contaminated environments⁵⁴. These applications benefit from the materials' high stability, ease of synthesis,

Table 6. MP2/AVDZ binding energies of the two-body and three-body complexes (E_b , kcal/mol).

Complex	E_{int}	$E_{int} + ZPVE$	Complex	E_{int}	$E_{int} + ZPVE$
Oxazole-CO ₂			Oxazole-CO ₂ +N ₂		
I1	-4.48	-3.95	I1I5	-5.94	-5.13
I2	-3.13	-2.74	I1I2A	-6.18	-5.40
			I1AI2B	-6.23	-5.44
			I1AI2B	-6.57	-5.70
			I1AI1A	-6.57	-5.71
			I1AI3	-8.40	-7.31
Oxazole-N ₂			Oxazole-N ₂ +CO ₂		
I1A	-1.91	-1.51	I1AI1A	-4.85	-4.09
I1B	-1.94	-1.56	I1A I4	-3.93	-3.26
I2A	-1.61	-1.28	I1B I4	-4.81	-3.98
I5	-1.40	-1.03	I2A I4	-3.60	-2.99
			I1B I2	-5.03	-4.354

and ability to be modulated into various shapes and sizes. This section focuses on investigating the mechanisms of adsorption and activation of CO₂ and N₂ by metal clusters, Au₆ and Cu₆, as well as on the metal oxide Zn₃O₃. To bolster the CO₂ and N₂ adsorption capability, this choice of cluster was motivated by the tendency of clusters with an even number of particles to demonstrate higher stability compared to their odd-sized counterparts, along with possessing a larger HOMO-LUMO gap⁵⁵⁻⁵⁷. Moreover, these clusters exhibit a rapid increase in binding energies with increasing cluster size. Notably, these nanoparticles possess the ability to bind with various biological or medicinal molecules containing relevant heteroatoms like nitrogen and oxygen, all while exhibiting low toxicity⁵⁸. The CO₂/N₂-Oxa@Au₆, Cu₆, or Zn₃O₃ complexes were initially formed by attaching the stable structure of two distinct complexes, namely I1 (Oxa@CO₂) and I1A (Oxa@N₂), to the most stable form of Au₆, Cu₆, and Zn₃O₃ (a planar triangle with D3h symmetry), using electron-rich positions such as N^{56,57,59,60}. Harmonic vibration frequencies were also calculated at the same theoretical level to identify the obtained structures as local minima. Figure 4 displays the optimized structures for Oxa@Au₆, Cu₆ and Zn₃O₃ and for CO₂/N₂-Oxa@Au₆, Cu₆ and Zn₃O₃. This figure shows that in the Oxazole@cluster structure, the gold, copper, or zinc atoms situated at the apex of the octahedron forms a covalent bond interaction at the O4 positions of the oxazole molecule. As seen in Figure 4, both gases are physically adsorbed, and the I1 and I1A structures of the Oxa@CO₂ and Oxa@N₂ complexes are moderately perturbed by the presence of the cluster. Consequently, in the structure I1@Au₆, I1@Cu₆, the hydrogen bond between the

oxygen O10 and H6 of the oxazole breaks, and a new hydrogen bond forms between O11 and H7 of the oxazole. The calculated MP2/AVDZ/ LanL2DZ BEs of the CO₂/N₂-Oxa@Au₆, Cu₆ and Zn₃O₃ complexes are listed in the Table 7. Our results show that metallic and metal oxide clusters favor the adsorption of CO₂ and N₂ gases. In hexametall clusters, the adsorption energies (E_b) reach a maximum with the Cu₆ cluster, at -6.46 kcal/mol for CO₂ and -10.25 kcal/mol for N₂. However, the Au₆ and Zn₃O₃ clusters exhibit similar binding energy values: $E_b(\text{Au}_6@I1) = -4.58$ kcal/mol and $E_b(\text{Zn}_3\text{O}_3@I1) = -4.56$ kcal/mol for CO₂, and $E_b(\text{Au}_6@I1) = -2.19$ kcal/mol and $E_b(\text{Zn}_3\text{O}_3@I1) = -2.22$ kcal/mol for N₂. This is highly advantageous as it allows for the replacement of expensive gold clusters with more cost-effective materials such as Zn₃O₃.

Adsorption of CO₂ and N₂ in the metal and metal oxide surfaces (III)

The Molecular simulation (Monte Carlo) was conducted to examine the adsorption of CO₂ and N₂ on Au, Cu, and ZnO (111) surfaces. The choice of Au and Cu surfaces (111) is motivated by the interest in the interaction of small molecules Au (111) surface. Furthermore, adsorption on noble metals (such as Cu, Ag, and Au) is considered a promising avenue for materials in futures technologies and applications⁶¹, however, the selection of ZnO aims to ensure high efficiency in the low-cost adsorption of pollutants. The investigation commenced with optimizing the geometries of the Oxa@CO₂ and Oxa@N₂ complexes using the COMPASS II force field in the Forcite Module. Subsequently, we constructed three-layer models for each surface (Au(111), Cu(111), and ZnO(111)).

Figure 4. Optimized structures of Oxa@Au₆, Cu₆ and Zn₃O₃ and of CO₂/N₂-Oxa@Au₆, Cu₆ and Zn₃O₃ complexes at MP2/AVDZ/LanL2DZ method.

Table 7. MP2/AVDZ/LanL2DZ binding energies of the CO₂/N₂-Oxa@Au₆, Cu₆ and Zn₃O₃ complexes (E_b , kcal/mol).

		Au ₆	Cu ₆	Zn ₃ O ₃
Complexes	I1	I1	I1	I1
Oxazole@CO ₂	-4.48	-4.58	-6.46	-4.56
Oxazole@N ₂	-1.77	-2.19	-10,25	-2.22

In the Adsorption Locator Module, we selected one of these surfaces and added the adsorbate, either Oxa@CO₂ or Oxa@N₂, before running the calculations. This process was repeated for all surfaces. The optimized geometries and their corresponding adsorption energies are depicted in the Figure 5. The calculations show spontaneous physisorption of CO₂ and N₂. Furthermore, the ZnO surface is the most favorable for N₂ adsorption compared to CO₂, with an adsorption energy reaching -151.62 kcal/mol for N₂, while for CO₂, it reaches a value of -148.01 kcal/mol. However, for the two other surfaces, Cu (111) and Au (111), the adsorption of CO₂ is more favorable than that of N₂, with respective adsorption energy values of -36.97 kcal/mol and -32.88 kcal/mol for Au, and -22.27 kcal/mol and -19.52 kcal/mol for Cu (111). Overall, our calculations demonstrate that the surfaces of gold (Au), copper (Cu), and zinc oxide (ZnO) are capable of adsorbing N₂

and CO₂ from gas mixtures. Moreover, ZnO and Cu offer advantages in terms of adsorption capacity for both gases, without introducing additional cost-related issues.

Conclusion

In summary, our study focused on two-body van der Waals complexes Oxa@CO₂ and Oxa@N₂, as well as three-body complexes CO₂@Oxa@N₂ and Oxa@CO₂@clusters (Au₆, Cu₆, and Zn₃O₃), using the Møller-Plesset perturbation theory (MP2) method with AVTZ and AVDZ basis sets. Our calculations reveal that oxazole exhibits adsorption capacity for both gases. Examination of the binding energies shows a significantly higher CO₂ adsorption capacity compared to N₂. Furthermore, the presence of a second gas does not alter the oxazole's ability for simultaneous capture of both gases, but may enhance adsorption through hydrogen bonding formation among the three systems. Adding clusters Au₆, Cu₆, and Zn₃O₃ to the most stable structures I1 of the Oxa@CO₂ complex and I1A of the Oxa@N₂ complex increases the adsorption capacity for both gases, with Cu₆ exhibiting the highest capacity compared to Au₆ and Zn₃O₃. Finally, the investigation of interactions between the most stable structures of the Oxa@CO₂ and Oxa@N₂ complexes with the three (111) surfaces of Au, Cu, and ZnO demonstrates that gold (Au), copper (Cu), and zinc oxide (ZnO) surfaces are capable of adsorbing N₂ and CO₂ from gas mixtures. Moreover, ZnO and Cu offer advantages in terms of adsorption capacity for both gases, without introducing additional cost-related issues.

Figure 5. Optimized structures of Oxa@ Au (111) /Cu (111) and ZnO (111) and of CO₂/N₂-Oxa@ Au (111)/ Cu (111) and ZnO (111) complexes, derived from the MC simulation.

Ethics and consent

Ethics and consent were not required.

Data availability statement

No data are associated with this article

Acknowledgements

The authors acknowledge the CTI of Universidad Autónoma de Chile and CSIC for computing facilities. And they express their gratitude to the Researchers Supporting Project (RSPD2024R808) of King Saud University, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia.

References

- Altintas C, Avci G, Daglar H, *et al.*: **An extensive comparative analysis of two MOF databases: high-throughput screening of computation-ready MOFs for CH₄ and H₂ adsorption.** *J Mater Chem A*. 2019; **7**(16): 9593–9608. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Li JR, Sculley J, Zhou HC: **Metal-Organic Frameworks for separations.** *Chem Rev*. 2012; **112**(2): 869–932. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Keskin S, van Heest TM, Sholl DS: **Can Metal-Organic Framework materials play a useful role in large-scale carbon dioxide separations.** *ChemSusChem*. 2010; **3**(8): 879–891. [PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Li JR, Kuppler RJ, Zhou HC: **Selective gas adsorption and separation in Metal-Organic Frameworks.** *Chem Soc Rev*. 2009; **38**(5): 1477–1504. [PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Nugent P, Belmabkhout Y, Burd SD, *et al.*: **Porous materials with optimal adsorption thermodynamics and kinetics for CO₂ separation.** *Nature*. 2013; **495**(7439): 80–84. [PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Bae YS, Snurr RQ: **Development and evaluation of porous materials for Carbon dioxide separation and capture.** *Angew Chem Int Ed Engl*. 2011; **50**(49): 11586–11596. [PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Wang J, Huang L, Yang R, *et al.*: **Recent advances in solid sorbents for CO₂ capture and new development trends.** *Energy Environ Sci*. 2014; **7**(11): 3478–3518. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Rowsell JLC, Yaghi OM: **Metal-Organic Frameworks: a new class of porous materials.** *Microporous Mesoporous Mater*. 2004; **73**(1–2): 3–14. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- James SL: **Metal-Organic Frameworks.** *Chem Soc Rev*. 2003; **32**(5): 276–288. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Shen Y, Pan T, Wang L, *et al.*: **Programmable logic in Metal-Organic Frameworks for catalysis.** *Adv Mater*. 2021; **33**(46): 2007442. [PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Belmabkhout Y, Guillerm V, Eddaoudi M: **Low Concentration CO₂ capture using physical adsorbents: are Metal-Organic Frameworks becoming the new benchmark materials?** *Chem Eng J*. 2016; **296**: 386–397. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Qiu S, Xue M, Zhu G: **Metal-Organic Framework membranes: from synthesis to separation application.** *Chem Soc Rev*. 2014; **43**(16): 6116–6140. [PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Farha OK, Eryazici I, Jeong NC, *et al.*: **Metal-Organic Framework materials with ultrahigh surface areas: is the sky the limit.** *J Am Chem Soc*. 2012; **134**(36): 15016–15021. [PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Younas M, Rezakazemi M, Daud M, *et al.*: **Recent progress and remaining challenges in post-combustion CO₂ capture using Metal-Organic Frameworks (MOFs).** *Prog Energy Combust Sci*. 2020; **80**: 100849. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Wang Y, Wang X, Wang X, *et al.*: **Effect of functional groups on the adsorption of light hydrocarbons in fmj-type Metal-Organic Frameworks.** *Cryst Growth Des*. 2019; **19**(2): 832–838. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Razavi SAA, Morsali A: **Linker functionalized Metal-Organic Frameworks.** *Coord Chem Rev*. 2019; **399**: 213023. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Howarth AJ, Liu Y, Li P, *et al.*: **Chemical, thermal and mechanical stabilities of Metal-Organic Frameworks.** *Nat Rev Mater*. 2016; **1**(3): 15018–15032. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Sant'Ana AC, Santos PS, Temperini MLA: **The adsorption of squaric acid and its derived species on silver and gold surfaces studied by SERS.** *J Electroanal Chem*. 2004; **571**(2): 247–254. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Kim J, Oliver AG, Neumann GT, *et al.*: **Zn-MOFs containing Pyridine and Bipyridine Carboxylate organic linkers and open Zn²⁺ sites.** *Eur J Inorg Chem*. 2015; **2015**(18): 3011–3018. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Asif M, Sajid H, Kosar N, *et al.*: **Effect of fluorination on the adsorption properties of aromatic heterocycles toward methyl halides: a quantum chemical study.** *Comput Theor Chem*. 2021; **1204**: 113394. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Dalbouha S, Boussefi R, Komiha N, *et al.*: **Stability of van der Waals complexes of the greenhouse effect gases NH₃, SO₂ and CO with imidazole in gas mixtures containing CO₂.** *Comput Theor Chem*. 2017; **1099**: 8–13. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Boussefi R, Dalbouha S, Timón V, *et al.*: **Stability of Van der Waals complexes of the greenhouse effect gases CH₄ and SF₆ with imidazole in gas mixtures containing CO₂.** *Comput Theor Chem*. 2016; **1094**: 82–91. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Timón V, Senent ML, Hochlaf M: **Structural single and multiple molecular adsorption of CO₂ and H₂O in Zeolitic Imidazolate Framework (ZIF) crystals.** *Microporous Mesoporous Mater*. 2015; **218**(6759): 33–41. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- El Houda Bensiradj N, Timón V, Boussefi R, *et al.*: **DFT studies of single and multiple molecular adsorption of CH₄, SF₆ and H₂O in Zeolitic-Imidazolate Framework (ZIF-4 and ZIF-6).** *Inorg Chim Acta*. 2019; **490**: 272–281. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Izzaoui S, El Makarim HA, Benoit DM, *et al.*: **Theoretical study of the CO₂ adsorption by Zeolitic Imidazolate Frameworks (ZIFs).** *J Phys Chem C*. 2017; **121**(37): 20259–20265. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Boulmène R, Prakash M, Hochlaf M: **Microscopic investigations of site and functional selectivity of triazole for CO₂ capture and catalytic applications.** *Phys Chem Chem Phys*. 2016; **18**(43): 29709–29720. [PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Vogiatzis KD, Mavrandonakis A, Klopper W, *et al.*: **Ab initio study of the interactions between CO₂ and N-Containing Organic Heterocycles.** *Chemphyschem*. 2009; **10**(2): 374–383. [PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Chen L, Cao F, Sun H: **Ab Initio study of the π-π interactions between CO₂ and Benzene, Pyridine, and Pyrrole.** *Int J Quantum Chem*. 2013; **113**(20): 2261–2266. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Li G, Wang Z: **Naphthalene-based Microporous Polyimides: adsorption behavior of CO₂ and toxic organic vapors and their separation from other gases.** *J Phys Chem C*. 2013; **117**(46): 24428–24437. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Agarwal RA, Gupta NK: **CO₂ sorption behavior of imidazole, benzimidazole and benzoic acid based coordination polymers.** *Coord Chem Rev*. 2017; **332**: 100–121. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Zhang JP, Zhang YB, Lin JB, *et al.*: **Metal azolate frameworks: from crystal engineering to functional materials.** *Chem Rev*. 2012; **112**(2): 1001–1033. [PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Britt D, Furukawa H, Wang B, *et al.*: **Highly efficient separation of carbon dioxide by a metal-organic framework replete with open metal sites.** *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*. 2009; **106**(49): 20637–20640. [PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Zhang FM, Dong LZ, Qin JS, *et al.*: **Effect of Imidazole arrangements on proton-conductivity in Metal-Organic Frameworks.** *J Am Chem Soc*. 2017; **139**(17): 6183–6189. [PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Liu S, Yue Z, Liu Y: **Incorporation of imidazole within the metal-organic framework UiO-67 for enhanced anhydrous proton conductivity.** *Dalton Trans*. 2015; **44**(29): 12976–12980. [PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Zhang HZ, Zhao ZL, Zhou CH: **Recent advance in oxazole-based medicinal chemistry.** *Eur J Med Chem*. 2018; **144**: 444–492. [PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Ali MU, Gong Z, Ali MU, *et al.*: **Fossil energy consumption, economic development, inward FDI impact on CO₂ emissions in Pakistan: testing EKC hypothesis through ARDL model.** *Int J Financ Econ*. 2021; **26**(3): 3210–3221. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- de Vries W: **Impacts of nitrogen emissions on ecosystems and human health: a mini review.** *Curr Opin Environ Sci Health*. 2021; **21**(7): 100249. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Rincon L, Hasmy A, Marquez M, *et al.*: **A perturbatively corrected tight-binding method with hybridization: application to gold nanoparticles.** *Chem Phys Lett*. 2011; **503**(1–3): 171–175. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Wang Y, Zhou G: **DFT Investigations of Au_n Nano-Clusters supported on TiO₂ Nanotubes: structures and electronic properties.** *Molecules*. 2022; **27**(9): 2756. [PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Chenga X, Li F, Zhao Y: **A DFT investigation on ZnO clusters and nanostructures.** *J Mol Struct: THEOCHEM*. 2009; **894**(1–3): 121–127. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Frisch MJ, Trucks GW, Schlegel HB, *et al.*: **Gaussian 09 Revision C.01.** Gaussian Inc., Wallingford CT, 2010. [Reference Source](#)
- Material studio.** BIOVIA, 2020. [Reference Source](#)
- Prokhorenko S, Kalke K, Nahas Y, *et al.*: **Large scale hybrid Monte Carlo simulations for structure and property prediction.** *npj Comput Mater*. 2018; **4**(1): 80. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Møller C, Plesset MS: **Note on an approximation treatment for Many-Electron Systems.** *Phys Rev*. 1934; **46**(6): 618–628. [Publisher Full Text](#)

45. El Hadki H, Gámez VG, Dalbouha S, *et al.*: **Theoretical spectroscopic study of acetyl (CH_3CO), vinyloxy (CH_2CHO), and 1-methylvinyloxy (CH_3COCH_2) radicals: barrierless formation processes of acetone in the gas phase [version 2; peer review: 2 approved]. *Open Res Eur.* 2022; **1**: 116.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)**
46. Kendall RA, Dunning TH Jr, Harrison RJ: **Electron affinities of the first-row atoms revisited. systematic basis sets and wave functions.** *J Chem Phys.* 1992; **96**(9): 6796–6806.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
47. Boys SF, Bernardi F: **The calculation of small molecular interactions by the differences of separate total energies. Some procedures with reduced errors.** *Mol Phys.* 1970; **19**(4): 553–566.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
48. Grev RS, Janssen CL, Schaefer HF: **Concerning zero-point vibrational energy corrections to electronic energies.** *J Chem Phys.* 1991; **95**(7): 5128–5132.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
49. Chiodo S, Russo N, Sicilia E: **LANL2DZ basis sets recontracted in the framework of density functional theory.** *J Chem Phys.* 2006; **125**(10): 104107.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
50. Nakazawa T: **Current understanding of the global cycling of carbon dioxide, methane, and nitrous oxide.** *Proc Jpn Acad Ser B Phys Biol Sci.* 2020; **96**(9): 394–419.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
51. Nolan M: **Alkaline earth metal oxide nanocluster modification of rutile TiO_2 (110) promotes water activation and CO_2 chemisorption.** *J Mater Chem A.* 2018; **6**(20): 9451–9466.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
52. Wang D, Kou R, Choi D, *et al.*: **Ternary self-assembly of ordered metal oxide-graphene nanocomposites for electrochemical energy storage.** *ACS Nano.* 2010; **4**(3): 1587–1595.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
53. Shabatina T, Vernaya O, Shumilkin A, *et al.*: **Nanoparticles of bioactive metals/ metal oxides and their nanocomposites with antibacterial drugs for biomedical applications.** *Materials (Basel).* 2022; **15**(10): 3602.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
54. Mohammadi MD, Patsalidis N, Bhowmick S, *et al.*: **Adsorption of air pollutants onto silver and gold atomic clusters: DFT and PNO-LCCSD-F12 calculations.** *RSC Adv.* 2023; **13**(26): 18014–18024.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
55. Baishya S, Deka RC: **Exploring structures, electronic and reactivity properties of Au_nH_n ($n = 1-12$) clusters: a DFT approach.** *Comput Theor Chem.* 2012; **1002**: 1–8.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
56. Ahmed AA: **Structural and electronic properties of the adsorption of nitric oxide molecule on copper clusters Cu_n ($N = 1-7$): a DFT study.** *Chem Phys Lett.* 2020; **753**: 137543.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
57. Oymak H, Erkoç S: **Group 12 elements and their small clusters: electric dipole polarizability of Zn, Cd and Hg, Zn_2 dimer and higher Zn_n microclusters and neutral, cationic and anionic zinc oxide molecules (ZnO , ZnO^+ and ZnO^-).** *Int J Mod Phys B.* 2012; **26**(8): 1230003.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
58. Sapsford KE, Algar WR, Berti L, *et al.*: **Functionalizing nanoparticles with biological molecules: developing chemistries that facilitate nanotechnology.** *Chem Rev.* 2013; **113**(3): 1904–2074.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
59. Manzoor D, Pal S, Krishnamurthy S: **Influence of charge and ligand on the finite temperature behavior of gold clusters: a BOMD study on Au_5 cluster.** *J Phys Chem C.* 2013; **117**(40): 20982–20990.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
60. Nhat PV, Nguyen PTN, Si NT: **A computational study of thiol-containing cysteine amino acid binding to Au_6 and Au_8 gold clusters.** *J Mol Model.* 2020; **26**(3): 58.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
61. Li J, Zhao T, Chen T, *et al.*: **Engineering noble metal nanomaterials for environmental applications.** *Nanoscale.* 2015; **7**(17): 7502–7519.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)